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Challenges To Combating Cyber Security Threats In Nigeria 2010–2023

Abdulmalik Ozomata, Dr. Joseph Ezekiel Obuje, Dr. Ahmed Abubakar II & Dr. Sankira Musa

Department of History and International Studies,
Faculty of Arts,
Federal University of Lafia, Lafia, Nigeria
Emails: absan4u@gmail.com, ezekielobuje@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The increasing dependence on digital technology in governance, finance, and communication has made cyberspace an essential component of national development and security. In Nigeria, the rapid expansion of internet use and digital infrastructure since 2010 has been accompanied by a growing wave of cyberattacks targeting government institutions, financial systems, and private organisations. This development poses an emerging threat to Nigeria's national security, with implications that transcend economic loss to include political instability, data breaches, and erosion of public trust. The problem that necessitates this study lies in the persistent rise of cyberattacks in Nigeria despite the existence of the Cybercrimes Act of 2015 and the establishment of several institutional frameworks. The aim of this research is to appraise cyberattacks as a growing threat to national security in Nigeria from 2010 to 2023. The specific objectives are to examine the nature and trends of cyber-attacks within the period under review; assess the adequacy of Nigeria's legal and institutional response; and evaluate the impact of cyber insecurity on national stability. The study adopts a qualitative methodology, drawing on secondary data from government publications, policy documents, journal articles, and international cybersecurity reports. Findings reveal that weak institutional coordination, low technical capacity, and limited public awareness have hindered effective response to cyber threats. The study concludes that without a comprehensive national cybersecurity strategy that integrates public and private sector collaboration, Nigeria's national security will remain vulnerable in the digital age.

Keywords: Cyber security, Crimes, Government Institutions and National security

INTRODUCTION

The modern era has seen the advent of the amalgamation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) scenario that has become the defining engine of world development by influencing how governmental structures transact governance, communication, and economic businesses as well as systems of security. The 21st century which is often described as the digital era has seen a growing convergence between physical and digital systems whereby countries have come to rely heavily on digital networks in getting basic services and performing administrative roles.¹ Nevertheless, as this reliance on digital technologies has been more than growing, it has simultaneously created severe weaknesses which cybercriminals and other malicious actors use, making cyber-attacks one of the fastest-growing global security menaces. The internet is also the key channel that allows such interactions as it acts as a critical

¹ Taddeo, Mariarosuaaria. *The Ethics of Cybersecurity*. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2019), 34.

communication source, commercial services, healthcare delivery, education, and other important services. The degree to which life in the present-day world relies on the development of the supporting technological systems is significant.² However, these intensive uses of ICT have provided risks to systems and services to cyber criminals, hence providing avenue to serious criminal activities.

The emergence of the digital age has transformed the way societies communicate, conduct business, and manage information. In Nigeria, the period between 2010 and 2023 witnessed a remarkable increase in internet usage, mobile telecommunications, digital banking services, electronic commerce, and social networking platforms.³ These developments contributed significantly to economic growth, financial inclusion, and the modernization of public and private institutions. However, the expansion of digital technologies also created new avenues for cybercriminal activities, making cybersecurity an increasingly important issue within Nigeria's national security framework.

During this period, Nigeria experienced various forms of cyber threats, including online fraud, identity theft, phishing attacks, cyber extortion, data breaches, malware attacks, and unauthorized access to sensitive information. The growing sophistication of cybercriminals, coupled with the interconnected nature of modern information systems, exposed weaknesses in the country's cybersecurity environment.⁴ As individuals, businesses, and government institutions became more dependent on digital platforms, the consequences of cyberattacks became more severe, affecting economic activities, public confidence, and national security.

Although the Nigerian government introduced several initiatives aimed at strengthening cybersecurity through legislation, institutional reforms, and policy development, the effectiveness of these measures has remained a subject of debate.⁵ Efforts to combat cyber threats have often been constrained by inadequate technological infrastructure, insufficient funding, shortage of skilled cybersecurity personnel, weak enforcement of existing regulations, and limited public awareness of cybersecurity practices.⁶ Furthermore, the borderless nature of cyberspace has complicated efforts to investigate and prosecute cybercriminals whose activities frequently extend beyond national jurisdictions.

This study examines the challenges associated with combating cybersecurity threats in Nigeria between 2010 and 2023. It explores the extent to which government policies, security agencies, private organizations, and international partnerships have addressed the growing problem of cybercrime. The study also investigates the factors responsible for the persistence of cybersecurity threats despite numerous interventions implemented during the period under review.

Findings from this research indicate that while Nigeria recorded notable progress in developing cybersecurity policies and institutional frameworks, significant obstacles continued to undermine effective implementation. The study reveals that inadequate cybersecurity awareness, limited technical capacity, poor inter-agency coordination, insufficient investment in cybersecurity infrastructure, and the constantly evolving tactics of cybercriminals remained major barriers to successful cybersecurity management. Consequently, the persistence of these challenges contributed to the continued vulnerability of Nigeria's digital space, highlighting the need for more comprehensive and sustainable cybersecurity strategies.

² A. Adekunle and A. Olabode. "Cybersecurity Threats and the Nigerian Media Landscape: An Empirical Study". *Journal of Cybersecurity Research*, 6, no.2, (2021): 85-102.

³ C. C. Eze and O. R. Eze. Assessment of Nigeria's Media Landscape in the Information Age, Cyberspace, and Cyber Security: Challenges and Prospects. *Madonna University Journal of Social Sciences*, 1, no. 1(2025)

⁴ A. Adekunle and A. Olabode. "Cybersecurity Threats and the Nigerian Media Landscape: An Empirical Study". *Journal of Cybersecurity Research*, 6, no.2, (2021): 85-102.

⁵ Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC). 2025. "Nigeria Faces 70% Broadband Penetration Target Despite Mounting Challenges." *RegTech Africa*, June 2025

⁶ O. A. Shodunke. "Globalization and National Security: Challenges for Nigeria." (A Research Project Submitted to National Defense College, Nigeria, August 2010

Conceptualization:

Cyber Attacks

The term “cyber-attack” has attracted widespread scholarly attention as the expansion of digital technologies has reshaped global security landscapes. Although the expression is used frequently in media, policy, and academic discourses, its meaning varies, depending on disciplinary focus like Computer Science, Criminology, International Relations, or Security Studies. To achieve conceptual precision, it is necessary to examine how different scholars have defined the term and what analytical dimensions they emphasize.

One of the most commonly cited definitions of the concept of cyber-attack can be found in Clarke and Knake, who define it as a nation-state-level attack in which a hacker is able to disrupt or damage the computers or networks of the other country. This definition places cyber-attacks in a larger context of national security, with a focus on state interest and bad motives. Others claim, however, that it is too narrow since it only concentrates on state actors, thus because cybercrimes or terrorism activities without government sponsorship.⁷

National Security

National security is a concept that has stood the test of time and been a controversial idea in the field of political science and international relations. Its significance has changed with the times following the changes in world politics, the development of technologies, as well as the emergence of new threats. In the past, national security was largely concerned with protecting the territorial integrity and the sovereignty of a state against external military aggression. In the modern society, however, especially the advent of non-conventional dangers like terrorism, pandemics and cyber-attacks, the concept has come to be broadened to include economic, political, environmental, and social levels of safety and stability.

Early realist scholars, such as Hans Morgenthau,⁸ national security was perceived through the military might and state Independency. According to Morgenthau, the process of power acquisition was the key to the existence of a state in an anarchic world system. According to this classical school of thought, the national security was understood as the power of a nation to protect itself against the attack of external forces by means of military force and deterrence. Although a powerful strategy, it has however been criticized as being narrow in its scope since it is blind on internal weaknesses and non-military threats that have the power to put a Volvo on a state.

Objectives of Cybersecurity attacks in Nigeria

1. Cybersecurity aims to protect information and digital assets by preventing unauthorized access, theft, alteration or destruction of sensitive of sensitive data belonging to individuals, businesses and government institutions.
2. Cybersecurity ensures confidentiality, integrity and availability of information by implementing appropriate security measures that safeguard data from cyber from cyber threats and ensure it remains accurate and accessible to authorized users.
3. To support economic growth and digital transformation by creating a secure digital environment that encourages electronic commerce, online banking, digital innovation and investment.
4. Cybersecurity helps in building resilient ecosystem by encouraging collaboration among government agencies, private organizations, educational institutions and international partners in addressing emerging cyber threats.

⁷ R. A. Clarke and R. Knake, *Cyber War: The Next Threat to National Security and What to Do About It*, Reprint edition (New York: Ecco, 2012), 6.

⁸ Hans Morgenthau, *Politics Among Nations: The Struggle for Power and Peace*. (New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 1948)

Challenges to combating cybersecurity threats in Nigeria

The challenges facing cyber security attacks in Nigeria includes: Technological gaps, inadequate legal framework, Lack of requisite skill, Technological advancement, Lack of public and private sector cooperation, Jurisdiction, Weak implementation of cybersecurity laws and Socio-economic factor.

1. Technological gaps

It is a factual challenge of combating cybersecurity threats because developed digital economies have enormous technological distance between Nigeria and their centralized digital economies. The internet penetration has been rising fast, reaching approximately 55 percent as per the NCC in 2023, but even then, the cybersecurity infrastructure of the country is lax and poorly developed.⁹ The vast majority of government institutions and private organizations of the country use outdated software and outdated hardware with poor network systems which are very susceptible attacks. There are no latest security architectures to contain these vulnerabilities, including intrusion detection system, firewall, and sophisticated data encryption systems.

This is being expressed through the fact that the level of automation and intelligence in cyber defense systems is low. Contrary to most developed economies where AI and Machine Learning solutions are implemented on real-time threat detection, Nigerian cybersecurity policies are reactive and not proactive. Most of the agencies are unable to foresee or identify breaches before damage has escalated to extreme proportions. In addition, the country has a general lack of cybersecurity labs, digital forensics centers, and secured data stores. This renders organized responses against cyberattacks sluggish and ineffective in some cases.

2. Inadequate legal framework

The other critical issues that face the fight against cybersecurity threat in Nigeria is the weakness of the legal framework that is in place. Although cyber-attacks are becoming more common and more advanced in their methods, there are legal and institutional infrastructures that lack development and implementation in Nigeria. The adequacy lack is reflected in the oldness of laws, their weak implementation ability, lack of jurisdiction, and disconnect with the global cybersecurity requirements. These loopholes have enabled a scenario in which cybercriminals are working with a relative impunity undermining national security and the economy.¹⁰

In these respects, it must be noted that the legislature of Nigeria made a good step in 2015 with the help of the new bill called Cybercrime (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act; it was the first time when Nigeria had a full-fledged law regarding crimes involving computer systems and other digital resources. Nevertheless, in his book, *Cybersecurity Law and Practice in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects*, Ndukwe Kalu states that despite the rather progressive character of the Act on paper, it has certain vulnerabilities regarding its enforcement and the complementary role of the institution.¹¹ Concerning the Act, Kalu notes that clear spheres of accountability to various implementing agencies are not defined and this can trigger interagency conflicts and low institutional efficiency between institutions involved in the implementation process like the Nigerian Police Force, Economic and Financial Crimes Commission and National Information Technology Development Agency. The Act has advantages in the form of the hacking to identity theft inclusions, but it has the drawback of lacking in operationalization. This paper builds on the arguments presented by Kalu on the fact that what Nigeria does not have is a lack of laws but lack of a coordinated and effective enforcement system.

⁹ World Bank. *Nigeria Digital Economy Diagnostic: A Plan for Building Nigeria's Inclusive Digital Future*. Washington, DC: World Bank, 2019

¹⁰ Olayinka, Solomon E. *Legal and Institutional Challenges to Cybersecurity in Africa: A Nigerian Perspective*. (Abuja: Centre for Cybersecurity Studies, 2020)

¹¹ Kalu Ndukwe *Cybersecurity Law and Practice in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects*. (Lagos: Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies Press, 2019)

Also, the judiciary and other law enforcing agencies in Nigeria are largely lacking special knowledge to read and apply these cybercrime laws in response. According to *Global Cyber Law in Practice: The Road to Harmonization*, by Michael L. Rustad, a combination of legal and technical expertise is required to effectively bring criminals of cybercrimes to justice.¹² As long as Nigerian courts were ill equipped to deal with digital evidence and cyber forensics, many law enforcers are not trained in electronic investigation techniques. This skilling gap also expands the enforcement gap between being legal and practice.

3. Lack of Requisite skill

The unavailability of the necessary technical and professional expertise by the individuals upon who the responsibility to offer protection to the digital infrastructure of the Nigerian Nation is entrusted to ranks at the list of the most enduring obstacles to effective cybersecurity management in the country. This type of cybersecurity work requires very specialized skills—a set of high-level technical skills, analysis of digital forensics, analytical politics, and legal expertise. Unluckily, Nigeria lacks deep background of such trained professionals both on the governmental scale, and in the private one. This lack undermines the capabilities of the nation to foresee, identify and react to cyber threats to leave critical infrastructures exposed to any form of attack by domestic and foreign forces.

According to National Information Technology Development Agency- NITDA, Nigeria has a gap in workforce on cybersecurity, reporting a gap of 90.6 percent, meaning that the number of people demanding the skill of cybersecurity professionals is vastly higher than the number of people with the skills.¹³ Better still, the lack of government institutions is severe and most of the ICT people do not have the relevant training about network security, data encryption and incident response procedures, this means that digital systems in ministries, financial institutions, security agencies, etc. are frequently vulnerable to malware, ransomware and phishing attacks. Moreover, NCC affirmed that the cases of cybercrime have been on the increase every year because of the poor human resource in preventing and mitigating these problems.

4. Technological Advancement

The use of new technologies has become absolutely important on the world economic arena. Cybercrime is an issue to modern economic growth and this necessitates the need to safeguard the world economy to mitigate and eradicate this new technology facilitated crime that has seemingly become a more prevalent phenomenon. The use of a computer or some other related technology, including a personal device, is also useful in committing cybercrimes. It is in this regard that the legislators need to update their definition of a computer as provided in the Nigerian cybercrime (Prohibition and Prevention) act, 2015 to cover portable devices. It is posited that this omission has resulted in the legal backlash of new cybercrimes in Nigeria being difficult on the technological perspective.¹⁴

5. Lack of Public and Private Sector cooperation

The cooperation between the government and the business should also be guaranteed by the national legislation to combat cybercrime. Compared to the laws established by the government, e.g., the cybercrime (Prohibition and Prevention) act 2015, the benefits of private regulation include mobility, flexibility, and environmental sensitivity, market dynamics, effectiveness, and less governmental regulation are all points to consider. On the other hand, the cyberspace could not be wholly controlled without the government intervention to some extent. As an example, the cybercrime (Prohibition and Prevention) Act 2015 section 7 requires the operators of the cybercafe to register with the computer professional's registration council and even take records of the individuals who access the cybercafe to carry out online activities. Whilst this is a form of private regulation by cybercafe operators as mandated

¹² Rustad, Michael L. *Global Cyber Law in Practice: The Road to Harmonization*. (Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2015)

¹³ National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA). "Nigeria Faces 90.6% Cybersecurity Workforce Gap." *The Sun (Nigeria)*, July 10, 2025.

¹⁴ Adomi EE, Igun SE. Combating cybercrime in Nigeria. *Electronic Library*, 26, no.5, (2008):716-725.

by the government, it is reiterated that most internet activities are no longer carried out at the cybercafes as computers connected to the internet continue to rise. This has increased the distance between the private and the public sectors.¹⁵

6. Jurisdiction

Jurisdiction is one of the toughest and enduring problems of fight against cybersecurity threats in Nigeria. Cybercrimes are inherently transnational in nature, in that they go beyond geographical, legal and political borders. Cybercrimes, unlike traditional crimes that are committed within a territorial boundary, are in most cases committed by individuals or groups of individuals that carry them out at several countries all connected to the digital networks in such a way that they are not visible. This cross-national character of cyber game complicates the law enforcement processes in Nigeria because there are always doubts on which country has the legal jurisdiction to conduct any investigation, prosecute and convict cybercrimes.¹⁶ According to Kshetri, these principles have been over time growing insufficient to address cybercrimes whereby the perpetrator may be in a particular country, the victim may be in of individuals that carry them out at several countries all connected to the digital networks in such a way that they are not visible. This cross-national character of cyber game complicates the law enforcement processes in Nigeria because there are always doubts on which country has the legal jurisdiction to conduct any investigation, prosecute and convict cybercrimes.¹⁷

According to Kshetri, these principles have been over time growing insufficient to address cybercrimes whereby the perpetrator may be in a particular country, the victim may be in another country, and the servers may be in another country (Cybercrime and Cybersecurity in the Global South).¹⁸ The current legal framework of Nigeria, in particular, the Cybercrime (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act of 2015 attempts to address this complexity by claiming national jurisdiction over cyber-crimes that occur inside and outside of Nigeria provided that they impact the citizens and/or interests of the Nigerian citizens. As a matter of fact, though, the application of such extraterritorial clauses is hindered by a deficiency of global cooperation, the insufficiency of digital forensics and jurisdictional tensions with international governments.

7. Weak implementation of cybersecurity laws

The poor enforcement of the laws on cybersecurity in Nigeria is one of the most urgent issues in combating the increasing cybersecurity threats. Even though Nigeria has made some ample legislation moves, including the introduction of the Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act, 2015, there has been little enforcement, and it has been inconsistent and filled with institutional inefficiencies. Notwithstanding this act, cybercrime has only kept on the increase with Nigeria being ranked in top 10 countries in the world in cases of cyber fraud in various cybersecurity reports. This lack of connection can be partially explained by the inability of law use agencies, regulatory bodies, and judicial system to effectively and consistently enforce available cyber laws. Agencies such as the Nigerian Police Cybercrime Unit, the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), and the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA)¹⁹ are underfunded, lack technical expertise, and are often slow to investigate and prosecute cyber-related offenses. Synergy between agencies is also lacking and this leads to overlapping of jurisdiction, as well as the emergence of bureaucratic bottlenecks that hamper

¹⁵ Frank I, Odunayo E. Approach to cyber security issues in Nigeria: challenges and solution. *Int J Cogn Res Sci Eng Educ.* 2013;1(1): 100-110.

¹⁶ Nte ND, Enoke BK, Omolara JA. An Evaluation of the Challenges of Mainstreaming Cybersecurity Laws and Privacy Protection in Nigeria. *Journal of Law and Legal Reform.* 2022;3(2):243-266

¹⁷ Nte ND, Enoke BK, Omolara JA. An Evaluation of the Challenges of Mainstreaming Cybersecurity Laws and Privacy Protection in Nigeria. *Journal of Law and Legal Reform.* 2022;3(2):243-266

¹⁸ Kshetri, Nir, *Cybercrime and Cybersecurity in the Global South.* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2013)

¹⁹ Dayo Akindipe and Eteete Adam. Challenges in Regulating Emerging Cybercrimes in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology.* 2025

coordinated responses. Moreover, not all cybercrime cases are being reported or even investigated as people do not trust law enforcement or are afraid of the lengthy legal process with minimal outcome. On top of this, the judicial system in itself has a limited knowledge and ability to deal with cases of cybercrime. There is a low level of training of many judges and other legal practitioners on matters like handling digital evidence in the digital age, legal interpretation of cybersecurity laws, and intricacy of international operations of cybercrime. Such lack of knowledge causes unequal decisions, disqualification as a result of technicalities, and poor deterrence. In others, cybercriminals get away with offenses, be it due to loopholes in laws or by bribing their way out of prosecution, man as much as they have undermined the faith of the population in the system, they have emboldened offenders. The judicial procedure is also affected by the decrepit nature of the forensic instruments and absence of investment in the digital infrastructure needed to conduct an effective evidence collection. While digital forensics and tracing of data are being applied in the developed world to solve cyber heists within few days, in the cases of Nigeria, the institutions in the country very frequently have obsolete or manual systems. Furthermore, ignorance of their rights covered in the cybersecurity law, together with ignorance of the capacity-building programs, has implied that a significant portion of the population, particularly those in the business and financial sectors, do not know their rights. This loss of sense of law as a guide to practice leaves a loophole in the law that cybercriminals use to flourish. Nigeria is also hampered by the speedy domestication of local and multilateral cybersecurity arrangements to exchange cyber danger insights and prosecute cyber assailants over the boundary. These weaknesses on an institutional and structural level illustrate that, despite the fact that existing paper comprehensively, the cybersecurity laws will continue to be highly symbolic and inactive unless considerable gains are achieved in the implementation.

8. Socio-Economic factor

The high prevalence of socio-economic factors is one of the greatest struggles to the fight against cybersecurity threats in Nigeria which essentially defines both the vulnerability of the country to cybercrimes and weakens national cybersecurity activities. A large percentage of the Nigerian population is below the poverty line and such economic poverty has in most aspects contributed to the growth of cybercriminal activities. Joblessness, in this case, particularly among the youths, is particularly important in flaming cybercrime. Having little access to formal jobs and financial opportunities, a great number of educated and technologically aware young Nigerians resort to committing cybercrime as a way to survive.²⁰ Cyber fraud, often referred to as Yahoo Yahoo, has also developed into a sign of socio-economic desperation and even some communities eled their successful cybercriminals since, in some cases, they provide financial gain. This legitimization of cybercrime in some sectors of the society also adds more challenges towards curbing them by the government. Although the digital literacy and access to technology becomes an inherently good thing to have in a normal sense, in a situation of economic struggle and poor moral upbringing, the tools tend to find their way into wrong hands. Moreover, insufficient investment in education and digital infrastructure adds to the fact that Nigeria is susceptible to cyber threats. The resources required to provide either full cybersecurity training or even professional training in digital ethics are unavailable in many educational institutions throughout the country. Consequently, once the youth are exposed to technology, they tend to do so informally without being educated on responsible use as well as limits on legal and ethical use. The vacuum has enabled the prevailing negative cyber behaviour to stigmatize, and the lack of deterrence may be tied to a weak condemnation of the society and the little institutional check-ups.

CONCLUSION

The paper finds that cyber-attacks pose a new and more advanced menace to national security in Nigeria between 2010 and 2023. The more the country adopts digital technologies to govern its people, conduct business, military defense, and communication, the more it has become vulnerable to cyber risks.

²⁰ Dayo Akindipe and Eteete Adam. Challenges in Regulating Emerging Cybercrimes in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*. 2025

Cybercriminals and other formidable politically instigated forces have used the ineffective cybersecurity setup in Nigeria to penetrate sensitive government information, interfere with the electoral processes, defraud financial institutions and carry out surveillance of strategic national assets. The trends illustrate how the national security threats shifted over time to no longer pose as physical confrontations, but as borderless, invisible cyber warfare that can bring about devastating upheavals in the absence of a conventional weapon.

Among the key findings of the research is the single-out of structural and institutional flaws that do not help in ensuring that Nigeria is responding to the threat of cyber-attacks. Despite Nigeria enacting a number of the legal and institutional tools, including the Cybercrimes Act of 2015 and the creation of the Nigerian Computer Emergency Response Team (ngCERT), the implementation of their actions is rather ineffective. Lack of coordination of security agencies, absence of expert cybersecurity personnel, low awareness among people and inadequate budgetary allocation remains the bane to operations of securing the cyber infrastructure of the country. Such vulnerabilities have enabled syndicate organizations and other malice actors to take advantage of loopholes in the national cyber defense mechanism, which in most cases tend to have dire economic, political, and security overtones.

Moreover, the paper notes that cyber threats in Nigeria are not unique occurrences that exist independently but are connected to larger problems facing the country including terrorism, economic instability, political manipulation, and social unrest. Cyberspace has also been used by extremists and criminal groups to disseminate propaganda, recruit new adherents, coordinate attacks and conduct illegal financial transactions. Moreover, cyber-attacks carried out by political parties in election years pose a threat to the validity of the election process and bring about institutional mistrust. It is this overlap of cyber threats with other or in other forms of insecurity that makes a comprehensive and integrated approach in terms of security that is fully inclusive of cybersecurity necessary.

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